

Federated Learning for Workload Forecasting as enabler for Network Service Management

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Abstract—Next generation networks are expected to connect and manage a vast number of heterogeneous devices stretching over diverse and distributed technological domains (e.g., radio, transport, core), by embracing a ubiquitous presence of AI and ML within their operations. This shift imposes a significant challenge for the management and orchestration (MANO) frameworks in order to efficiently handle that great demand for computational power, particularly in the edge of the networks. Therefore, in order to increase the effectiveness of the task scheduling of the next generation networks it is crucial to proactively detect both periodic and non-periodic patterns that could affect the network’s decision-making processes. Previous research has been primarily based on centralized predictive models gathering all the data from the edge devices on one central processing point. Such approaches impose substantial communication overhead on the network, impacting bandwidth to the point of channel congestion, and exposing data to security vulnerabilities. This paper showcases a computational load forecasting method that aims to feed the MANO frameworks with predicted insights of the infrastructure state. The forecasting is performed by employing machine learning techniques such as LSTMs and Bi-LSTMs, by utilizing the federated learning family of algorithms, Fed-Opt, facilitating the distributed training process. The proposed method is evaluated with actual workload traces originating from a cluster of virtual machines. The experimental results show that the proposed federated learning approach provides results of comparable quality to the centralized learning methods, while minimizing the data exchanged between the edge nodes and the cloud.

Index Terms—CPU load, time-series forecasting, federated learning, edge cloud continuum, microservices

I. INTRODUCTION

The tendency of the sensing layer and subsequently the computation to shift towards the edge, introduce a growing complexity and diversity of the next-generation networks. This transition poses significant challenges for traditional centralized management and orchestration (MANO) methods in their pursuit to achieve high efficiency and sustainability. These tools heavily rely on the insights and patterns of the infrastructure’s usage to enable efficient resource management, prompting the exploration of innovative methods in predictive and prescriptive analytics within distributed network environments. The accurate prediction of different metrics such as CPU, memory, and bandwidth is of utmost importance for optimizing resource allocation, improving the network’s performance, and enabling proactive decision-making. Traditional

methods of microservices scheduling and mapping mostly rely on monitoring just the current state of the computational resources, or on the best-case scenarios, they engage centralized approaches, leading to increased communication overhead and potential privacy concerns due to the continuous data transmission.

Edge computing allows for distributed computing resources to be located closer to the data sources, enabling real-time processing and analysis. By placing computing power at the network edge, latency can be minimized, and bandwidth demands can be reduced, thereby enhancing system responsiveness and efficiency.

In order to combine the edge computing with machine learning, federated learning (FL) has emerged as a promising solution. FL, a decentralized learning paradigm, enables collaborative model training among edge devices without the need for data transfer to a central server. This approach allows for reducing communication overhead and leveraging the computational power available at the network’s edge. It also inherently complies with the data privacy constraint of the operators, who are often cautious with sharing data both for proprietary reasons and customer privacy requirements.

The main contributions of this paper are the following:

- an extensive performance analysis of FL algorithms (FedAvg, FedAdam, FedYogi and FedAdagrad) compared to centralized forecasting methods for predicting the computational load of a network spanning across the edge-cloud environment.
- the definition of a new metric, which along with other metrics, enables the evaluation of the overall performance of FL algorithms while incorporating the notion of network offloading.

The effectiveness and efficiency of the proposed framework is demonstrated through extensive experiments and evaluations. The results will showcase the benefits of leveraging FL in edge computing for CPU load forecasting, highlighting improvements in prediction accuracy, reduced communication overhead, and enhanced system performance. The findings of this research have the potential to contribute to the optimization of resource management in the distributed computing environments of the next generation networks, opening av-

enues for proactive decision-making and improved operational efficiency.

The work is structured as follows: Section II provides a literature review in the domain of CPU load forecasting and FL. Section III presents in detail both the centralized and the FL schemes implemented in this paper’s context. In Section IV, the experimental setup is described, along with the results and the performance evaluation. Last, Section V comprises the conclusion and future directions for research in this area.

II. RELATED WORK

The utilization of CPU workload forecasting techniques to effectively manage and orchestrate microservices and hardware resources across the computing and network continuum has garnered significant interest. Various studies have addressed the challenges of accurately predicting CPU load in dynamic computing environments.

Saxena et al. [1] conducted an extensive survey on the implementation of workload forecasting using different machine learning models. They analyzed the conceptual and operational design of these models, comparing their advantages and disadvantages. Calherios et al. [2] utilized ARIMA for workload prediction, taking into account quality of service (QoS) parameters such as response time and rejection rate. They evaluated the effectiveness of their approach in improving resource utilization and efficiency. Karim et al. [3] introduced a hybrid prediction model called BHyPreC, which combines a gated recurrent unit (GRU) with a bidirectional long short-term memory (BiLSTM) network to predict CPU usage workload in cloud virtual machines. This paper serves as a foundational basis for our research, as the BHyPreC model is incorporated in this work within the FL framework alongside other models.

Subramanya et al. [4] proposed prediction-based NFVI (Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure) scaling solutions in virtualized Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) environments. They applied various neural network (NN) techniques and employed federated learning for workload prediction. Although their work shares similarities with ours in terms of using FL techniques, we differentiate ourselves by studying a wider range of algorithms beyond FedAvg and evaluating the results by incorporating the concept of network offloading. Catena et al. [5] proposed a distributed NN solution where VNFIs’ processing capabilities are exchanged solely by sharing NN weights. Their approach differs from [4] and our work, as it employs a non-FL distributed framework with equal agents without the involvement of an aggregator in the weight exchange process. By reviewing these related works, it is evident that a more systematic evaluation is required for the methods used in predicting the computational workload in a decentralized manner.

III. COMPUTATIONAL LOAD FORECASTING

This section aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the various machine learning and FL techniques and methodologies employed facilitate the computational forecasting at the edge of the network.

A. Centralized Learning

1) *Linear Regression*: Linear Regression is a statistical technique used to model and analyze the linear relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent features. The goal of the algorithm is to estimate the best-fitting coefficients (slope and intercept) of the linear equation that minimize the difference between the target values (dependent variable) and the actual input data values (dependent variables). The basic form of a linear regression model can be represented as:

$$\hat{y} = \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_i x_i \quad (1)$$

where \hat{y} is the target value, x are the input data with $x_0 = 1$, β_0 is the intercept, while $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$ are the coefficients forming the slope of the line. It is a computationally cheap but widely used benchmarking approach since that, in many forecasting problems, outperforms more complex methods.

2) *Long Short-Term Memory Networks*: Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs) are NNs that introduce a memory cell which is responsible for storing and updating the information over time, along with a set of gating mechanisms. Those mechanisms can be divided into three parts: the input gate I , the forget gate f and the output gate O . The memory cell along with the gates and the activation function form the total LSTM unit, which processes and retains information, by capturing long-term dependencies and sequential patterns in the input data.

The above-mentioned gates are implemented as:

$$f_t = \sigma(x_t W_f + h_{t-1} U_f + b_f) \quad (2)$$

$$I_t = \sigma(x_t W_i + h_{t-1} U_i + b_i) \quad (3)$$

$$O_t = \sigma(x_t W_o + h_{t-1} U_o + b_o) \quad (4)$$

where x is the input data, h is the hidden state vector of the cell, matrices W and U contain respectively the weights of the input and recurrent connections, b are the bias vector parameters and σ is the sigmoid activation function.

The updates regarding the state of the cell c and the next state output h are performed as:

$$c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + I_t \odot \tilde{c}_t \quad (5)$$

$$h_t = O_t \odot \tanh(c_t) \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{c}_t = \tanh(x_t W_c + h_{t-1} U_c + b_c)$ and \odot is the element-wise product.

3) *Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory(Bi-LSTM)*: A Bi-LSTM is a specialized type of the LSTM family of NN architectures, that comprises two LSTM layers working in tandem. Each LSTM layer operates in a distinct direction: one processes the input sequence in a forward direction, while the other processes it in a backwards direction. This bidirectional approach allows the Bi-LSTM to consider both past and future information simultaneously. Compared to a traditional LSTM, the Bi-LSTM has the advantage of capturing a wider range of information by incorporating knowledge from both directions

and thus excels at capturing long-term dependencies and subtle relationships within sequential data.

The forward layer of a Bi-LSTM network considers the same mathematical equations as a simple LSTM network, having as input the new features x_t , the previous hidden state h_{t-1} and the previous cell state c_{t-1} . In the same way, the backward layer is based on the same equations with the difference that it utilizes the future hidden state value h_{t+1} with the current input data x_t . Thus, the backwards equations have the following form:

$$\overleftarrow{f}_t = \sigma(\overleftarrow{x}_t \overleftarrow{U}_f + \overleftarrow{h}_{t+1} \overleftarrow{W}_f) \quad (7)$$

$$\overleftarrow{I}_t = \sigma(\overleftarrow{x}_t \overleftarrow{U}_i + \overleftarrow{h}_{t+1} \overleftarrow{W}_i) \quad (8)$$

$$\overleftarrow{O}_t = \sigma(\overleftarrow{x}_t \overleftarrow{U}_o + \overleftarrow{h}_{t+1} \overleftarrow{W}_o) \quad (9)$$

$$\overleftarrow{c}_t = \overleftarrow{f}_t \odot \overleftarrow{c}_{t-1} + \overleftarrow{I}_t \odot \overleftarrow{c}_t^{\sim} \quad (10)$$

$$\overleftarrow{h}_t = \overleftarrow{O}_t \odot \tanh(\overleftarrow{c}_t) \quad (11)$$

where $\overleftarrow{c}_t^{\sim} = \tanh(\overleftarrow{x}_t \overleftarrow{U}_c + \overleftarrow{h}_{t+1} \overleftarrow{W}_c)$.

B. Federated Learning

FL operates as a decentralized approach that facilitates accumulating global knowledge from distributed clients. To initiate the process, a general or pre-trained model is distributed to the clients. Each client then utilizes its local data to train and creates a personalized model. Once the training is completed, the clients transmit their model's hyper-parameters back to the aggregator. The aggregator collects and combines all the updates received from the clients to construct an updated global model [6]. This ensures that the clients are consistently equipped with the latest global knowledge as it emerges.

Fig. 1. Federated learning scheme

Assuming that there are K clients participating in the FL procedure, each one equipped with a P_k set of indexes of data points and $n_k = |P_k|$, the optimization problem that needs to be solved is the following:

$$\min_{w \in \mathbb{R}^d} f(w) \quad (12)$$

where

$$f(w) = \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{n_k}{n} F_k(w) \quad \text{and} \quad F_k(w) = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{i \in P_k} f_i(w) \quad (13)$$

Typically, $f_i(w) = l(x_i, y_i; w)$ which is the loss function of the prediction example (x_i, y_i) made with model parameters w .

For the purposes of this paper, two FL algorithms are going to be studied: FedAvg and FedOpt.

1) *FedAvg*: FedAvg, introduced in [7], is a well-known and widely used FL algorithm. It relies on implementing the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithm to achieve convergence. During each round of training, FedAvg selects a fraction C of the clients and computes the gradient of the loss over the data held by these clients. The model weights w of client k are then updated locally using multiple epochs E of the formula $w^k = w^k - \eta \nabla f(w^k)$ where η is the learning rate.

After the number of local epochs is completed, the local weights are sent back to the aggregator, which constructs the new model by aggregating the local model weights of the selected clients. The algorithm restarts by returning the updated weights to the clients and selecting new random candidates.

Although FedAvg has exhibited good performance, recent studies have brought attention to its convergence challenges in certain scenarios [8]. These challenges arise from several factors, including client drift, i.e., Non-Independent and Identical (Non-IID) data distribution across clients, and lack of adaptivity to the data examined.

2) *FedOpt*: FedOpt is an evolution of FedAvg aiming to solve the above-mentioned drawbacks by introducing the notion of adaptive optimizers at both client and aggregator levels instead of using stochastic gradient descent for both operations. The algorithm's operation is based on the FedAvg algorithm by formulating the update equation on the aggregator's side as in eq. (14).

$$w_{r+1} = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{k \in S_r} w_r^k = w_r - \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{k \in S_r} (w_r - w_r^k) \quad (14)$$

Considering the differences $\Delta_r^k = w_r^k - w_r$ and $\Delta_r = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{k \in S_r} \Delta_r^k$, the FedAvg can be solved by applying the SGD to the $-\Delta_r$ with learning rate $\eta = 1$. This formulation permits the utilization of other learning rates and optimizers, as seen in the Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 FedOpt Implementation

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- 1: CLIENTOPT, SERVEROPT
 - 2: initialize w_0
 - 3: **for** each round $r = 1, 2, \dots$ **do**
 - 4: $S_r = (\text{random set of } m \text{ clients})$
 - 5: **for** each client $k \in S_r$ in parallel **do**
 - 6: **for** $j = 1, 2, \dots$ **do**
 - 7: Compute $g_{r,j}^k$
 - 8: $w_{r,j+1}^k = \text{CLIENTOPT}(w_{r,j}^k, g_{r,j}^k, \eta_l, r)$
 - 9: $\Delta_r^k = w_{r,K}^k - w_r$
 - 10: $\Delta_r = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{k \in S_r} \Delta_r^k$
 - 11: $w_{r+1} = \text{SERVEROPT}(w_r, -\Delta_r, \eta, r)$
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$g_{r,j}^k$ stands for the unbiased estimation of $\nabla F_k(w_{r,j}^k)$, while CLIENTOPT and SERVEROPT are the place holders for gradient-based optimizers with learning rates η_l for the client and η for the aggregator respectively. Thus, by adopting SGD for the ClientOpt and Adagrad, Yogi or Adam for the ServerOpt, the FedAdagrad, FedYogi and FedAdam algorithms are generated, respectively. The actual changes in Algorithm 1 take place in lines 8 (eq. 15) and 11 (eq. 16).

$$w_{r,j+1}^k = w_{r,j}^k - \eta_l \nabla l(w_{r,j}^k; b) \quad (15)$$

$$w_{r+1} = w_r + \eta \frac{m_r}{\sqrt{v_r + \tau}} \quad (16)$$

where $m_r = \beta_1 m_{r-1} + (1 - \beta_1) \Delta_r$, while:

$$v_r = v_{r-1} + (\Delta_r)^2 \quad (17)$$

$$v_r = v_{r-1} - (1 - \beta_2) (\Delta_r)^2 \text{sign}(v_{r-1} - (\Delta_r)^2) \quad (18)$$

$$v_r = \beta_2 v_{r-1} + (1 - \beta_2) (\Delta_r)^2 \quad (19)$$

By selecting one of the eq. 17, 18 and 19, we derive the algorithms of Adagrad, Yogi, and Adam, respectively. The parameter τ controls the algorithms' degree of adaptivity, with smaller values of τ representing higher degrees of adaptivity, while β_1 and β_2 are the decay rates of the average of the gradients ($\beta_1, \beta_1 \in \{0, 1\}$).

C. Losses and Metrics

During the whole building, training and testing procedure of both centralized and FL models, the same loss functions, activation functions, and evaluation metrics were used to provide the results in a common and comparable base.

1) *Loss Function*: The Huber loss function, also known as the smoothed mean absolute error, is a loss function commonly used in regression tasks, particularly in situations where the data may contain outliers or noise. It can be thought of as a combination of the squared error loss and the absolute error loss.

The mathematical equation that implements this loss is defined as follows:

$$L_\delta = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(y - \hat{y})^2, & \text{if } |(y - \hat{y})| < \delta \\ \delta((y - \hat{y}) - \frac{1}{2}\delta), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where y is the true value, \hat{y} is the predicted value, and delta is a hyper-parameter that determines the threshold for switching from quadratic to linear loss.

The Huber loss is less sensitive to outliers compared to the squared error loss, as it behaves like the absolute error loss for large errors (greater than delta) and like the squared error loss for small errors (less than or equal to delta). This makes it a robust alternative for regression problems where the presence of outliers or noisy data can affect the regression capabilities of the model.

2) *Evaluation Metrics*: The evaluation metrics that were used in both centralized and FL models were the Mean Squared Error (MSE), the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and

the Coefficient of Determination (R^2). MSE and MAE are computed as follows:

$$MSE = \sum_{i=1}^D (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad MAE = \sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i| \quad (21)$$

while R^2 coefficient is measured as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (22)$$

In the metrics described above, n is the number of data points, y_i represents the true value of the i -th data point, \hat{y} is the predicted value and \bar{y} is the mean value of y_i .

Finally, in this paper, an overall criterion is proposed in order to evaluate the models more adequately. As the MAE metric offers the most objective view of the models' performance, it is combined with the communication cost CC of the learning procedure to compose the new criterion ϕ . The mathematical formulation of this criterion is:

$$\phi = MAE \cdot CC \quad (23)$$

The communication cost is defined as the burden that the learning procedure imposes on the communication network for the required data to travel from their source up to the point of processing. It is considered that the CC for the centralized models is equal to 1 because all the data travel to the central node. For the FL part, the CC is thought as the size of the parameters exchanged between the server and the clients in bytes, multiplied by two (to include both steps 1 and 3 of Fig. (1)) and divided by the total amount of bytes of the dataset. Thus, the communication cost CC is calculated as:

$$CC = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{centralized learning} \\ \frac{1}{D} \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{k=1}^S 2P, & \text{federated learning} \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

where D is the total size of the data set, P is the number of parameters exchanged in bytes. Finally, R is the total number of rounds, S is the random set of clients in each round and K the total amount of clients.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Experiment Setup

The experiments were conducted in a cloud-native compliant lab environment where K3s [9], a lightweight distribution of Kubernetes, was employed to unify the underlying computing infrastructure. This infrastructure is constituted by:

- one server equipped with an Intel® Core™ i9-12900F processor, an NVIDIA RTX A5000, 64GB RAM and 1TB disk capacity.
- one worker computer equipped with Apple M1 processor with integrated GPU, 16GB RAM and 256GB disk capacity.
- four Raspberry Pi 4 equipped with ARM processor, 4GB RAM and 64GB disk capacity.

To leverage the computational power of the graphics card and expedite time-consuming procedures, the centralized models were trained and tested on the server. In the case of FL models,

all available nodes were utilized, with the server acting as the aggregator. The rest of the infrastructure hosts the twenty-two clients that are engaged in the experiment as microservices.

The dataset used for the purposes of this paper is the one provided by Bitbrains in [10]. This real-life dataset concerns traces originating from VMs that are connected to a fast storage area network (SAN) with storage devices located over a distributed data center.

This dataset is in csv format for each VM, providing eleven exogenous values of CPU, memory, disk and bandwidth. The column "CPU Usage Percentage" is the selected input to obtain the needed information and perform the forecasting algorithms described in this paper.

In terms of preprocessing, the data were checked for missing values, abnormal values (e.g., negative values or values surpassing 100%) and outliers. No scaling action was performed as the data is already in the percentage scale.

The initial dataset was split into training, testing, and validation sets, with the size of 70%, 20% and 10% of the total data, respectively. The training set is used for the model to fit the data, the testing set is used to provide the early results to fine-tune the models, while the validation set is used to benchmark and compare the final versions of the models. The testing set is only used in the centralized part of this paper to provide the best hyper-parameters for the ML models. Those hyper-parameters are directly passed in the models of the FL part, where local training and validation sets are available to each client, while the server only has access to the validation data of every client.

The time interval between two consecutive data measurements is 300ms; therefore, the chosen input and output windows are set as 30 seconds and 15 seconds, respectively. In practical terms, this means that 100 data measurements are used as input for the models, while 50 predictions are provided to be compared with future measurements. Conduct-

Fig. 2. Convergence analysis for NNs

ing a convergence analysis on the centralized NN allowed us to identify the optimal number of epochs for training. The outcomes of this analysis are presented in Figure 2. It

was observed that four epochs of training yielded satisfactory results for LSTM and BiLSTM models. Similarly, five epochs were found to be suitable for achieving desirable outcomes with the BHyPreC model. Finally, ten repetitions of the FL procedure were considered enough for the local models to converge.

B. Performance Evaluation and Discussion

In terms of the centralized models, all of them are closely aligned with the patterns of the dataset's timeseries. The bar chart in Figure 3 demonstrates that linear regression achieves the lowest MSE on the testing data, while BiLSTM performs best in terms of the validation data. On the other hand, BiLSTM attains the optimal MAE values for both testing and validation data. The R^2 metric, scaled up by a factor of 10 for better visualization in the figure, exhibits minimal differences among the models, with BiLSTM delivering the most favorable result. Subsequently, BiLSTM seems to have the best overall performance while utilizing a centralized structure with access to all the data, exhibiting a mean absolute deviation of 1.41%.

Fig. 3. Centralized models analysis

of machine learning models showcased in tables I and II, better results are evident with linear regression (mentioned as LR in the tables and figures), particularly in terms of MSE. Among the NNs, BiLSTM showcases the best performance. The inferior performance of the NNs can be justified by the constrained access to data, as each client model is exclusively trained on the timeseries of the single client. Consequently, this limitation hinders the generalization of their knowledge. When

TABLE I
FEDERATED LEARNING MSE

	FedAvg	FedAdagrad	FedYogi	FedAdam	Mean
LR	66.94	116.35	105.08	48.18	93.31
LSTM	182.93	273.01	323.54	247.02	175.74
BiLSTM	172.62	194.57	106.59	207.78	170.29
BHyPreC	139.25	154.40	328.26	233.80	213.93
Mean	140.43	184.19	144.15	184.58	

considering the FL algorithms, FedAvg consistently delivers superior outcomes in both MAE and MSE, regardless of the deployed model. Among the FedOpt family of algorithms,

FedYogi exhibits a more favorable performance compared to FedAdam and FedAdagrad. It is important to note that results in this phase of deployment may vary due to the stochastic client selection during distributed training and evaluation sessions.

The predictive ability of the FL approach is always poorer than centralized learning, but this needs to be anticipated as the training is performed in particular set of data for each client. This is why a notable mention needs to be made for the combination of linear regression with FedAdam, which yields the best-distributed results that are comparable to those of centralized learning. The last mean of evaluation that

TABLE II
FEDERATED LEARNING MAE

	FedAvg	FedAdagrad	FedYogi	FedAdam	Mean
LR	4.93	5.37	4.95	2.53	4.72
LSTM	4.64	6.10	7.44	5.95	6.03
BiLSTM	4.82	5.96	5.88	6.76	5.86
BHyPreC	6.01	6.51	8.13	11.84	8.12
Mean	5.10	6.88	5.99	6.77	

is employed is ϕ . All the FL algorithms explored in this paper have the same amount of exchanged parameters in each step, thus the communication cost CC is only affected by the machine learning model parameters. For example, linear regression in the FL environment exchanges $2 \cdot 10$ learning rounds $\cdot 22$ clients $\cdot 72$ bytes of parameters $\div 6095296$ bytes of the dataset $\cong 0.005$.

As seen in table III, the substantial difference in the order of magnitude of data exchanged between the centralized and FL models, along with the relatively smaller variation observed in terms of MAE, contributes to the favorable evaluation of the metric ϕ in the context of the FL scheme. This disparity highlights the efficient utilization of resources and the ability to achieve comparable levels of predictive accuracy in FL despite the reduced communication requirements. Consequently, the consideration of ϕ in FL compensates for the accuracy benefits of traditional centralized approaches (also exhibiting a lack of privacy).

TABLE III
METRIC ϕ COMPARISON

	Centralized			Federated		
	CC	MAE	ϕ	CC	MAE	ϕ
Lin. Regression	1	2.22	2.22	0.005	4.72	0.115
LSTM	1	1.51	1.51	0.007	6.03	0.273
BiLSTM	1	1.42	1.42	0.007	5.86	0.257
BHyPreC	1	1.54	1.54	0.021	8.12	1.409

V. CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results demonstrate that the FL approach achieves accurate and robust CPU load forecasting in an network service environment for efficient network management, approaching the results of traditional centralized methods. Metric ϕ proves that this deployment offer better results for

the overall computational and network environment, than the centralized learning, even if the forecasting accuracy is mildly poorer.

Moreover, the distributed nature of FL makes the solution scalable and adaptable, as the number of clients grows. On the contrary, centralized models in such a scenario would need excessive computational power to support the training part, while also cumbering the network channels.

This solution could be extended by adopting of visual transformers for the learning part, such as the one in [11], as they can discover hidden patterns in the time series with less data available in comparison with the NNs used in this paper. In addition the exploration of pure networking data as input for the algorithms, such as bandwidth or latency, could be of great interest in order to provide a holistic future view of the underlying network infrastructure to the MANO frameworks.

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